

D7.3: Promotional activities and engagement report 2

WP7 – Dissemination, Communication and Diffusion

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Executive summary

This document is an overview of the performed Dissemination and Communication activities M17-M37. It reports on performed activities and actions related to the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (D7.1) that was developed within the framework of Task 7.1 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication strategy, WP7 – Dissemination, Communication and Diffusion.

Through promotion of results a wide audience was reached, and a significant number of relevant stakeholders were actively engaged. A significant number of tools were deployed including the BEACON project website, BEACON Social Media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube) and BEACON promotional materials (brochure, one-pager, banner).

Moreover, the engagement tools that were created include BEACON Content Hub, Newsletters, Press releases, Polls, Podcasts and Publications in scientific and business journals. Additionally, consortium members participated in numerous Agri industry conferences, summits and business & professional events. The engagement of Agricultural Insurance Enablers: BEACON Advisory Board and BEACON Lighthouse Customers Group (LHCs) significantly boosted the dissemination of results.

Results were being closely monitored throughout the course of the project and the dissemination team timely targeted specific stakeholder groups to maximise impact. The KPIs have been achieved and the project has succeeded in a dynamic interaction with the targeted audiences that ensure a long-term impact and market-uptake of the project outcomes.

1. Introduction

Communication and Dissemination activities are important to project components, as achieving desired impact is to a large degree dependent on engaging target end-users during project activities and generating interest as a foundation for commercial exploitation activities post-project.

To maximize impact with every interaction, the BEACON Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan (DEC) was delivered early in the project's lifetime (D7.1 - M3), wherein a coherent strategy was defined.

Thus, a multi-step and multi-channel dissemination strategy was followed to reach different target groups, with an emphasis on a wide geographic coverage. The basic principles underlying BEACON'S DEC were simplicity and consistency of interactions tailored to the right person – at the right time – in the right environment.

Figure 1. The BEACON ecosystem of stakeholders

To maximize impact with given resources, the effectiveness of various outreach activities was monitored, evaluated and adjusted to the level of need and involvement of different target groups throughout project implementation, treating the DEC as a living document.

Figure 2. The BEACON dissemination activities aim

Furthermore, the following Key Performance Indicators were the guidance of walking a successful path to achieve all aims.

Figure 3. Key Performance Indicators and target values

Figure 4. The BEACON website homepage

Following the project progress, the website was being updated on a regular basis in six main page sections, and various subsections as shown in the tree below.

Figure 5. BEACON website tree

Concept	About	Services	Intranet	News & Media	Contact us
	Project			Latest News & Newsletters	
	Work Packages & Deliverables			BEACON Content Hub	
	Pilot Activities			Publications	
	Lighthouse Customers				
	Timeline				
	Advisory Board				
	Partners				

Webpage visits as well as the general performance of the BEACON webpage have been tracked using Google Analytics. See below the relevant statistics.

Until 20 January 2022, the website counted 26,242 pageviews and more than 6,520 users, located in 110 different countries around the globe.

Figure 6. BEACON website pageviews

Figure 7. BEACON website users

Facebook page

<https://www.facebook.com/beaconh2020/>

BEACON’s Facebook page was created on 22/4/2019, for establishing direct communications with target audiences, both in terms of relevant groups (e.g., Agricultural Insurance Brokers) as well as individuals, and other audiences’ segments. Although Facebook is considered as the main channel for communications of individuals, the BEACON Facebook page served for broader communications, as well as B2C ones.

Until 21 January 2022, BEACON has published more than 270 posts. See below a sample of them.

Figure 8. Facebook page

Figure 9. Facebook indicative posts

Twitter account

https://twitter.com/BEACON_Ag

The BEACON Twitter account has been used for amplifying communications to a large community of active stakeholders, as well as for propagation of news and project developments. Regular Twitter chats focused on attracting and engaging with target audiences leading also to the establishment of a trusted BEACON network, enlarging the outreach to broad and targeted audiences.

Figure 10. Twitter account

The followers base may be categorized in four main groups, specifically private companies, research – academia, relative research projects and individuals of relative to the project activities. It needs to be noted that BEACON has achieved networking with a number of Horizon 2020 Projects through its Twitter account and they are namely:

- | | | |
|---------------------------------|-------------|---------------|
| agROBOfood | EXCALIBUR | ROSIN |
| ARCH - Saving Cultural Heritage | FAIRshare | Salsa |
| ATLAS | i2connect | SCALIBUR |
| BACCHUS | INDUCE | SIEUSOIL |
| Block.IS | IoT4Potato | SmartAgriHubs |
| CANDELA | LandSense | Stargate |
| CitieS-Health | LANDSUPPORT | STARTUP3 |
| DEEP | Lift | STOP-IT |
| DEMETER | MIND STEP | SURE-Farm |
| DESIRA | OPEN DEI | Swinostics |
| DIONE | OPTAIN | TRUSTS |
| Ecobreed | OPTIMA | UPSCALE |
| EFFECT | PANACEA | URBIOFIN |
| Envision | Pledger | Wateragri |
| e-shape | PoliRural | WaysTUP! |

Figure 11. Indicative tweets

LinkedIn Group & Page

<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13699653/>
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/66655087/admin/>

BEACON has both a group and a page account, extensively used for networking purposes, enabling the promotion of BEACON amongst a broad community of professionals within AgI as well as other segments of BEACON’s target audiences. Furthermore, the accounts have achieved interaction with representatives of other relevant groups such as: Agricultural Insurance; Agribusiness and Farm Insurance Specialist (AFIS), Agricultural Insurance – Academic group etc., enhancing its outreach and engagement with other target audiences.

Figure 12. LinkedIn account

Figure 13. LinkedIn Indicative posts

BEACON H2020 Project
 107 followers
 100+ posts

BEACON H2020 Project publications series in peer-reviewed journals and conferences

Almeida Zafra, A. F., Benito Zafra, R. M., Quemada Sáenz-Badillos, M., Losada, J. C., and Tarquis Alfonso, A. M. "Revealing climate and vegetation indices interactions through Cross Recurrence Techniques. EGU General Assembly 2021, online, 19-30 Apr 2021, EGU21-12723 <https://lnkd.in/g/2Xb3h3>

Access all papers and presentations here <https://lnkd.in/g/5cczJ8G>

Karavas Underwriting Agency AgroApps PC ETAM S.A.
 Universidad Politécnica de Madrid Etheric InsSens doo

#EUAgri #EU_H2020 #H2020 #HorizonEU #Blockchain #Agtech #Eu #Agribusiness #Eo #RedesigningAgri #Agri_Innovation #Agri #Cropinsurance #Innovation #Insurance #fintech #ICT #BigData #EIPagri #earthobservation #remotesensing #Insurtech #DSMeu #InvestEUResearch #EUeic #EIEu

BEACON H2020 Project
 107 followers
 100+ posts

Country focus

Crop insurance policies in France cover a wide range of climatic perils

For more updates of other countries' insurance schemes, visit our content hub <https://lnkd.in/g/9p8q7>

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#EUAgri #EU_H2020 #H2020 #HorizonEU #Blockchain #Agtech #Eu #Agribusiness #Eo #RedesigningAgri #Agri_Innovation #Agri #Cropinsurance #Innovation #Insurance #fintech #ICT #BigData #EIPagri #earthobservation #remotesensing #Insurtech #DSMeu #InvestEUResearch #EUeic #EIEu

BEACON H2020 Project
 107 followers
 100+ posts

Under the spotlight

Azerbaijan Memorandum of cooperation signed between the Insurers Association & the Agricultural Insurance Fund

<https://lnkd.in/g/9QH-38>

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#EUAgri #EU_H2020 #H2020 #HorizonEU #Blockchain #Agtech #Eu #Agribusiness #Eo #RedesigningAgri #Agri_Innovation #Agri #Cropinsurance #Innovation #Insurance #fintech #ICT #BigData #EIPagri #earthobservation #remotesensing #Insurtech #DSMeu #InvestEUResearch #EUeic #EIEu

BEACON H2020 Project
 107 followers
 100+ posts

The BEACON_H2020_Project meeting will take place tomorrow

An opportunity to discuss the project progress and next steps

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#EUAgri #EU_H2020 #H2020 #HorizonEU #Blockchain #Agtech #Eu #Agribusiness #Eo #RedesigningAgri #Agri_Innovation #Agri #Cropinsurance #Innovation #Insurance #fintech #ICT #BigData #EIPagri #earthobservation #remotesensing #Insurtech #DSMeu #InvestEUResearch #EUeic #EIEu

BEACON H2020 Project
 107 followers
 100+ posts

BEACON flew to the US

Details here <https://lnkd.in/g/NNEtFg>

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#EUAgri #EU_H2020 #H2020 #HorizonEU #Blockchain #Agtech #Eu #Agribusiness #Eo #RedesigningAgri #Agri_Innovation #Agri #Cropinsurance #Innovation #Insurance #fintech #ICT #BigData #EIPagri #earthobservation #remotesensing #Insurtech #DSMeu #InvestEUResearch #AgriResearchEU #H2020SC2 #EUeic

BEACON H2020 Project
 107 followers
 100+ posts

More on the BEACON H2020 Project Toolbox

<https://lnkd.in/g/D4MTV>

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#EUAgri #EU_H2020 #H2020 #HorizonEU #Blockchain #Agtech #Eu #Agribusiness #Eo #RedesigningAgri #Agri_Innovation #Agri #Cropinsurance #Innovation #Insurance #fintech #ICT #BigData #EIPagri #earthobservation #remotesensing #Insurtech #DSMeu #InvestEUResearch #EUeic #EIEu

YouTube Channel

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YkH130SVs0s>

The project's YouTube channel was created in October 2019, counting to date 33 videos, 29 of which were produced by the project and the rest come from other sources. All videos have reached more than 1,530 views so far.

Figure 14. YouTube channel

2.3 BEACON promotional material

The BEACON project has produced a series of promotional materials to enhance the promotion of the BEACON tools and services. Promotional materials have been used at project related and other events that BEACON partners were present, as well as in meetings and other project promotional activities.

These included logo, icons, two brochures one of an informative presentation of the project and a second one targeting business audiences, a one pager, a presentation template, a deliverable template, a letterhead, a press release template, a roll-up banner and a poster.

Figure 15. Sample of promotional material

THE ROLL-UP BANNER

THE POSTER

THE ONE PAGER

3. Engagement actions and outcomes

Ensuring a dynamic interaction with the BEACON targeted audiences was of utmost importance, to ensure a long-term impact and market-uptake of the project outcomes, with the BEACON consortium composition allowing access to all the categories of audiences. Direct and indirect access through the partners’ networks, ensured that the dissemination activities were effective and successfully achieved high reach and impact KPI’s.

The main target audience, AgI companies, were invited to participate and be actively engaged in the project through the “Lighthouse customers” group, being the first users of BEACON and further connecting the project to the AgI sector. Their active engagement and interaction within the project aimed at generating positive perceptions derived by the recognition of BEACON’s economic, social, and operational benefits. This not only worked as an amplifier in the dissemination of the project outcomes but also optimally enabled the creation of BEACON’s pool of potential future customers.

Engagement with other stakeholders potentially benefiting from the BEACON toolbox, services, and outcomes (in and out of the AgI sector), was also established mainly focusing on raising awareness and diffusing project advancements and results, creating interest and opportunities for further exploitation routes of BEACON’s solutions and outcomes.

24 engagements realised through 472 engagement invitations to insurance companies, farmers’ organisations, academics and other relevant stakeholders.

Figure 16. BEACON engagements

3.1 Newsletters

BEACON e-Newsletters were composed and published on the project website and social media, but were also distributed to the consortium members, Lighthouse customers, the “AgI Enablers” as well as networks and direct contacts within the BEACON ecosystem of stakeholders. The Newsletters served as a tool to communicate key updates and developments to the BEACON ecosystem of stakeholders and were aiming to keep them informed and engaged.

Every issue included several standard columns, such as:

- 🌱 Editorial
- 🌱 BEACON’s corner
- 🌱 Upcoming events
- 🌱 In case you missed
- 🌱 Join us

but also, supplementary columns, like the BEACON business cases, the BEACON lighthouse customers, and the latest updates focusing on subjects and news, relevant to the project.

All Newsletters can be found at <https://beacon-h2020.com/news-media/>.

Figure 17. Newsletters’ publication dates

Figure 18. Sample of Newsletters

REDEFINING AGRICULTURAL INSURANCE SERVICES
The BEACON project aspires to deliver a blockchain-fueled toolbox that couples...

LIGHTHOUSE CUSTOMERS
It is of utmost importance our services to be fitting the needs of the insurance and...

INTERVIEW WITH MR. GEORGE KARAVIAS
Mr. George Karavias is the CEO of Karavias Underwriting Agency and the BEACON project...

BEACON NEWSLETTER #1
Boosting Agricultural Insurance based on Earth Observation data

A new light in agro-insurance sector

Join us and stay informed about the latest project developments!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821964

Issue highlights

- The history of insurance and the genesis of agricultural insurance | p.2
- Risk assessment in the new CAP | p.4
- BEACON Lighthouse customers | p.6
- The BEACON advisory board | p.7
- BEACON Lighthouse poll #1 results | p.11

Happy New year 2022

BEACON NEWSLETTER #2
Boosting Agricultural Insurance based on Earth Observation data

A BEACON of light to smart Agri-Insurance

Welcome back to our BEACON project newsletter! Newcomers welcome!

Get to know about the history of agricultural insurance, and how risk assessment is implemented in the new CAP. Meet our project partner INOSENS and explore the opportunity to become part of the project Lighthouse Customers group!

Check out our YouTube videos, browse the BEACON project website and follow us on social media to learn more on our projects progress and findings.

Join us and stay informed about the latest project developments!

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Editorial ⌵

Project's progress ⌵

The AgrInsurance Meetup ⌵

Smart contracts for smart agriculture ⌵

BEACON's corner ⌵

Lighthouse Customers ⌵

Upcoming events ⌵

In case you missed ⌵

Join us ⌵

Editorial

Welcome to the third BEACON project newsletter!

Learn about the **AgrInsurance Meetup** that took place in Thessaloniki on the 12th of February.

Discover **Smart Contracts** and how fintech impacts the insurance industry through **Michiel Berende's**, CIO of the BEACON partner Etherisc, interview. Stay tuned with BEACON's **project progress** and get to know some of our **Lighthouse Customers**.

We invite you to regularly view our videos on YouTube, browse the project website which is rich in content and follow us on social media to learn more about our project's progress and findings.

Don't forget to join us and stay informed on the latest project developments!

Editorial ✎	<h2>Editorial</h2> <hr/> </div>
The BEACON Damage Assessment Calculator ✎	
The BEACON Lighthouse Customers ✎	
Upcoming events ✎	
In case you missed ✎	
Join us ✎	

Editorial ✎	<h2>BEACON's last chapter</h2> <hr/> <p>The BEACON project is coming to its end and after three years of implementation, we proudly present an account of our goals and results.</p> <p>BEACON's goals as visualized by the consortium were to enable the Agri sector to alleviate the effect of weather uncertainty when estimating the risk of Agri products, reduce the number of on-site visits for claim verification, reduce operational and administrative costs for monitoring of insured indexes and contract handling, as well as design more accurate and personalized contracts, by coupling Earth Observation technology with weather intelligence.</p> <p>The BEACON Intelligence Engine was designed, developed, and validated to complement the information used by insurance companies in their products and comprises of seven services:</p> <div style="display: grid; grid-template-columns: repeat(4, 1fr); gap: 10px;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Smart Contracts</p> </div> </div>
BEACON's corner ✎	
The BEACON business cases ✎	
BEACON's last chapter ✎	
Upcoming events ✎	
In case you missed ✎	
Stay in touch ✎	

Additionally, the Communication Team, initiated in October 2020 an ad hoc Newsletter/update, sent to all partners and subscribers' list through email, including highlights from the monthly project posts on the website and social media.

Figure 19. Email update sample

To increase the number of Newsletter subscribers, several sign-up campaigns have been developed in English and in all partners' languages to be more effective in attracting a wider audience.

Figure 20. Newsletter sign-up campaign sample

Figure 21. Newsletter sign-up cards sample translated in partner languages

German

Greek

Serbian

Spanish

INSTITUTION / ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
ETH Zurich	SWITZERLAND
EUPOLIS	GREECE
European Commission	BELGIUM
European University Cyprus	CYPRUS
eVineyard	SLOVENIA
Geminia insurance company limited	KENYA
Genillard & Co. GmbH	GERMANY
GEOTEE Branch of Eastern Macedonia	GREECE
GeoVille GmbH	AUSTRIA
GIC Re	INDIA
Globe Sensing	MEXICO
GS	GERMANY
GSI Ltd	UNITED KINGDOM
Hagel	AUSTRIA
HCP international	NETHERLANDS
Hellenic Agricultural Organization	GREECE
Hellenic Mediterranean University	GREECE
Hellenic Open University	GREECE
Hulling	UNITED STATES
IDS LTD	ΕΛΛΑΔΑ
INGO	UKRAINE
INSURANCE BROKER	GREECE
Insurance industry	GREECE
K M Dastur	UNITED KINGDOM
KU Leuven	BELGIUM
La Mobilière Insurance Company	SWITZERLAND
LFRZ	AUSTRIA
Ministry of Agriculture	CROATIA
Ministry of ecological transition	FRANCE
MunichRe syndicate limited	UNITED KINGDOM
NEUROPUBLIC	GREECE
National Observatory of Athens	GREECE
Office of Finnish Agriculture, Forestry and Cooperatives	FINLAND
OMICA s.r.l.	ITALY
OPEGIEKA	POLAND

INSTITUTION / ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
PeriSkion	GREECE
Prefecture of Pella	GREECE
Region Authority of Attica	GREECE
Region of Crete	GREECE
Region of Epirus	GREECE
ResCons ME & Globalesco	GREECE
respect - slovakia	SLOVAKIA
SIMA Software S.A.	BRASIL
South African National Space Agency	SOUTH AFRICA
Swiss Food Research	SWITZERLAND
Syneteristiki Ins sa	GREECE
Technological Institute of Crete	GREECE
Terroir from Space	ITALY
Thomason Machinery	CYPRUS
Universidad del Pacifico	PERU
University of Crete	GREECE
University of Kiel	GERMANY
University of Piraeus	GREECE
University of Reading	UNITED KINGDOM
University of São Paulo	BRAZIL
University of the Aegean	GREECE
VAA	THE NETHERLANDS
VISTA GmbH	GERMANY
VITO	BELGIUM
WARM Consulting Group	SWITZERLAND
Ypaithros - Chora SA	GREECE
Vatzianidou	GREECE
ELGO DIMITRA	GREECE

3.2 Press releases

Six press releases have been circulated during the project, to communicate important news of its development and to maximize awareness to both the main target audiences and the wider public.

Figure 22. Press releases

Press release #1 - December 2019 [\[link\]](#)

Press release #2 - March 2020 [\[link\]](#)

Press release #3 - July 2020 [\[link\]](#)

Press release #4 - December 2020 [\[link\]](#)

The BEACON toolbox: the ultimate solution for growing agricultural insurance business in the times of Covid-19

Climate change and various emergency situations, as well as the COVID-19 pandemic, are among the challenges currently facing Agri-Insurance (AgI) companies. Investing in research is a key to developing the best solutions.

The BEACON research project aims to develop a range of commercial tools and services for the AgI companies:

- supporting them to achieve a better risk and damage assessment within their AgI products
- enabling them to reduce the number of on-site visits for claims verification and to reduce their overall operational and administrative costs for monitoring and handling AgI contracts
- allowing them to design more accurate and personalized contracts.

BEACON, building upon state-of-the-art Earth Observation (EO), weather intelligence, ICT and Blockchain technologies, will provide insurance companies operating (or wishing to operate) in the AgI market, with robust and cost-effective tools and services to overcome serious limitations in the market.

BEACON will confidently empower AgI underwriting procedures and premium calculations, by providing access to, and analyzing EO, climate and localized meteorological data.

Using satellite-based information, coupled with weather intelligence and high-resolution weather forecast will enable an accurate damage assessment and claims adjustment along with a potential fraud detection.

Moreover BEACON, powered by Blockchain technology, will provide a Smart Contracts service, enabling an automated execution of contract clauses to insured parties, reducing administration costs and burden.

In the case of COVID-19, the BEACON Toolbox is designed to make the logistic work in the agri-insurance company more efficient, improving the staff distribution tasks through a better overview of damages that occur.

Press release #5 - July 2021 [\[link\]](#)

Έξυπνες λύσεις στη γεωργική ασφάλιση
δορυφορική τηλεπισκόπηση και τεχνολογία blockchain

Η γεωργική ασφάλιση είναι ο τομέας των ασφαλιστικών υπηρεσιών που εξαρτάται σε πολύ μεγάλο βαθμό από τις κλιματικές συνθήκες. Ο ολοκληρωμένος των ασφαλιστικών και η ανασταθίσιμη νέων προϊόντων εξαρτάται από τον καιρό και κατεύθυνση από τα ακραία καιρικά φαινόμενα.

Η εκτίμηση των ζημιών και ο χειρισμός των αποζημιώσεων είναι βαρύνοντες καθύστες ελέγχος και η επαύξηση τους απαιτεί εξειδικευμένες, Πολύπλες δε φορέες, τα αποτελέσματα των επιθεωρήσεων είναι αμφισβητούμενα.

Το προνοητικό έργο BEACON <https://beacon-h2020.com/en/> αναπτύσσεται με μεγάλη υπηρεσιών που συνδυάζει την τεχνολογία δορυφορικής τηλεπισκόπησης και την τεχνολογία blockchain παρέχοντας στις εταιρείες γεωργικής ασφάλισης ένα πλήρη και ολοκληρωμένο αυτοδυνατό σύνολο υπηρεσιών που τους εξοικονομεί τις επενδύσεις της αβεβαιότητας των καιρικών συνθηκών κατά την εκτίμηση των ζημιών. Επιπλέον αυτή η νέα υπηρεσιών και εργαλείων συμβάλει στη μείωση του αριθμού των επισκευών εκπαιδευμένων για την επαύξηση των απαιτήσεων αποζημιώσεων, καθώς και στη μείωση του διοικητικού κόστους παρακολούθησης των ασφαλιστικών ασφαλίσεων.

Το BEACON είναι επίσης η χρήση δορυφορικής τηλεπισκόπησης και τεχνολογίας Blockchain στη γεωργική ασφάλιση και μάλιστα το λειτουργικό κόστος των ασφαλιστικών εταιριών

Η εφαρμογή του BEACON πρόκειται να ενισχύσει την τεχνολογία blockchain, παραδίδοντας στους τελικούς χρήστες μια πρώτη ολοκληρωμένη έκδοση. Αυτή η πρώτη έκδοση θα διακρίνεται σε τρεις διαφορετικές πλατφόρμες εφαρμογών στη Σαυρία, την Ισπανία και την Ελλάδα. Σε κάθε μια ακολουθήθηκαν οι κατανοητές γρήγορες και καθυστερήσεις για τα καλύτερα σχέδια ώστε να διασφαλιστεί η επιτυχή εκτέλεση και η συλλογή ποσοτήτων πληροφοριών.

Η μοναδικότητα του BEACON έγκειται στην ολοκληρωτική προσέγγιση με την οποία ενσωματώνει τεχνολογικές καινοτομίες, παρέχοντας ένα χρήσιμο εργαλείο στους παρόχους γεωργικής ασφάλισης.

Αποστολή της Διεθνούς Δορυφορικής Τηλεπισκόπησης, το BEACON υπηρεσιών την τρέχουσα χρήση της τεχνολογίας και επιτυγχάνει την αξιοποίηση των κινδύνων και του βελτιώνει έκδοση σε αυτούς, την αποτελεσματικότητα διαχείριση των αποζημιώσεων, και μετατρέπεται τα παραδοσιακά υπηρεσιών γεωργικής ασφάλισης σε καινοτόμες τεχνολογικές λύσεις υψηλής προστιθέμενης αξίας.

Το BEACON είναι ένα πρώτο βήμα ολοκληρωτικής σε αυτή το ζώο με τη συμμετοχή φερώνων εταιριών από την Ελλάδα, την Ισπανία, τη Γαλλία και τη Σαυρία. Τα παραδοσιακά πληροφορίες επισκευές της προνοητικής έργο <https://beacon-h2020.com/en/> που στην συνέχεια μπορεί να υποβληθεί στην ηλεκτρονική διεύθυνση info@beacon-h2020.com

Press release #6 EN – January 2022 [\[link\]](#)

Redefining Agricultural Insurance Tools
The BEACON project is coming to an end, but its results will go on!

Following three years of implementation and two years of pilot iterations, as well as the validation of Pilot Data and Operational Data Products, the BEACON project is successfully reaching its end.

Results showed that BEACON toolbox managed to achieve in terms of service uptime and thus significantly reducing the Agricultural Insurance (AgI) process cycle-time, especially for contracts that covered calamities such as frost, flood, fire, and windstorms, minimizing the evaluation and the compensation / reimbursement time of a farmer to a week. For insured parcels under hail, BEACON toolbox offered a more accurate evaluation of damage under 40 days following the extreme event, bringing again time savings, even if not evident. On average it is estimated that the achieved AgI Process cycle-time decrease varies between 70% to 90%.

Similarly, the automation achieved within the AgI companies level reached more than 90% and could be increased further where the BEACON toolbox integrates directly with already utilized ERP and S&P systems. Automation among actors of the AgI supply chain was also piloted, and fully realized, achieving a 100% acceptance of data rate and information availability.

The BEACON Toolbox is ready to offer the AgI customers a list of clear benefits:

- Seamless contract monitoring** through better contract overview.
- More accurate climatology** and forecast dynamic statistics that assist underwriting and damage prevention in general.
- Better cost optimization** gained through higher operational efficiency:
 - better distribution of employees
 - prevention of in-field visits based on an accurate overview of damaged parcels
 - information about the damage before clients.
- Improved trust and transparency** among AgI supply chain actors by enabling the quick update of blockchain and through smart contracts handling.
- Higher consistency** of the whole AgI business pipeline.

BEACON's final message to its target AgI customers, through a now validated and proved definite value proposition, is that its toolbox couples leading earth observation technology with weather intelligence, and blockchain technology delivering cost-efficient and actionable insights for the agri-insurance industry, representing the end-to-end solution for AgI users.

The BEACON Horizon 2020 project started 3 years ago and lasts until this month. The project consortium was ANARRIS Underwriting Agency (Greece), AGROAPP FC (France), UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID (Spain), ENERGIE Océan (Germany), UNIVERSITY OF BUSINESS FACULTY OF CIVIL ENGINEERING (Greece), INOCON DOO NOVY SAD (Serbia) and ITAM (IT) (Greece).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant Agreement No. 822064.

Press release #6 EL – January 2022 [\[link\]](#)

ΔΕΛΤΙΟ ΤΥΠΟΥ
24/1/2022

Νέες τεχνολογίες στη Γεωργική Ασφάλιση
Το έργο BEACON ολοκληρώνεται και κεραυνοκοπάει τα αποτελέσματά του!

Τρία χρόνια μετά την έναρξη του BEACON και έπειτα από δύο χρόνια πιλοτικών πιλοτικών εφαρμογών, το έργο φτάνει με απόλυτη επιτυχία στο τέλος του.

Τα αποτελέσματα έδειξαν ότι η εφαρμογή BEACON αναφέρει με μεγάλη σημασία τον αποδοτικό χρόνο για την παροχή υπηρεσιών γεωργικής ασφάλισης, ειδικά για συμβόλαια που καλύπτουν καταστροφές όπως π.χ. παγετός, πλημμύρες, πυρκαγιές και ανεπιθύμητες αλλαγές καινοτομίες το χρόνο εκτίμησης και αποζημιώσεων των ασφαλισμένων.

Στα ασφαλισμένα για καλοκαιρινή θερμοκρασία η εργαλειοθήκη BEACON προσφέρει απόκριση αξιολόγησης της ζημίας σε χρόνο μικρότερο των 40 ημερών, επιφέροντας επιπλέον εξοικονομώμενο χρόνο. Κατά μέσο όρο εκτιμάται ότι η γρήγορη του χρόνου κυμαίνεται μεταξύ 70% και 90%.

Όμοια, η αυτοματισμένη ολοκλήρωση έφτασε το 90% και μπορεί να αυξηθεί περαιτέρω εφόσον η εργαλειοθήκη του BEACON ενσωματωθεί στα υφιστάμενα πληροφοριακά συστήματα των ασφαλιστικών εταιριών. Η αυτοματισμένη ολοκλήρωση μεταξύ των μερών της αλυσίδας της παροχής υπηρεσιών ασφαλιστικής, όπως η επικοινωνία των ασφαλιστικών εταιριών, επιτυγχάνοντας 100% απόδοση των αποτελεσμάτων και διαθεσιμότητα πληροφοριών.

Στα, η εφαρμογή του BEACON είναι έτοιμη να προσφέρει στον κλάδο της Γεωργικής Ασφάλισης μια σειρά από σημαντικά οφέλη:

- Αποδοτικότερη διαχείριση συμβολίων γεωργικής ασφάλισης** μέσω της καλύτερης παρακολούθησης τους.
- Αυξημένη σταθερότητα ανάμεσα ασφαλιστικών και μεταπωλητικών δεδομένων** που υποστηρίζουν την ποσοδομική διασφάλιση και τον καλύτερο χειρισμό τους.
- Βελτιστοποίηση κόστους** μέσω καλύτερης λειτουργικής απόδοσης:
 - καλύτερης των εργασιών
 - μείωσης των επισκευών επισκευών με βάση την ασφαλή εκτίμηση των καταστροφικών περιστατικών
 - εξοικονομώμενο σχετικά με τη ζημία κινδύνων των κλιμάτων.
- Βελτισμένη εμπιστοσύνη και διαφάνεια στις ασφαλιστικές εταιρείες** επιτρέποντας την σημασία της τεχνολογίας blockchain και διαφανή έλεγχο συμβολίων.
- Υψηλότερη συνέπεια** ολόκληρης της αλυσίδας υπηρεσιών γεωργικής ασφάλισης.

Η τελική μήνυση του έργου στους παρόχους γεωργικής ασφάλισης είναι ότι η εργαλειοθήκη του BEACON αποτελεί μια ολοκληρωμένη λύση που συνδυάζει την τεχνολογία δορυφορικής τηλεπισκόπησης με επαρκείς κλιματικές πληροφορίες και τεχνολογία blockchain, παρέχοντας αποδοτικές καινοτομίες και εξοικονομώμενες λύσεις για τον κλάδο της γεωργικής ασφάλισης.

Το έργο BEACON Horizon 2020 ξεκίνησε πριν από 3 χρόνια και ολοκληρώνεται αυτόν τον μήνα. Η ομάδα εργασίας του BEACON αποτελείται από ANARRIS Underwriting Agency (Greece), AGROAPP FC (France), UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID (Spain), ENERGIE Océan (Germany), UNIVERSITY OF BUSINESS FACULTY OF CIVIL ENGINEERING (Greece), INOCON DOO NOVY SAD (Serbia) και ITAM (IT) (Greece).

Το έργο έχει λάβει χρηματοδότηση από το πρόγραμμα έρευνας και καινοτομίας Horizon 2020 της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης στο πλαίσιο της συμβολής πληροφοριών αριθ. 822064.

Figure 23. Online and printed media publicity

3.3 BEACON Content Hub

BEACON value packed B2B content hub was a branded resources center created to help Agricultural Insurance players find the information they seek in the form they prefer. The hub was fueled by BEACON’s exclusive agri-insurance related content, acting as a showcase of resources – both technical and business related, and was divided into three main sections: VIDEOS, INFO CARDS and RELEVANT UPDATES.

Videos Section

The Content Hub’s video section counts 26 videos of BEACON production, all of them also uploaded on the project’s YouTube channel, alongside 7 more videos produced from external sources.

Figure 24. Content Hub Videos

January 24, 2022 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos
BEACON Toolbox – A turn key solution for Agricultural Insurance

November 5, 2021 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos
BEACON publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences

May 26, 2021 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos
BEACON 3rd Business Case, KARAVIAS, Greece

April 27, 2021 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos
BEACON 2nd Business Case – Triglav, Serbia

March 26, 2021 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos
BEACON 1st Business Case – Agroseguero, Spain

February 8, 2021 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos
THE BEACON TOOLBOX – Boosting Agricultural Insurance

December 28, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos
BEACON methodologies for damage assessment

November 30, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos
Blockchain support to Agri-Insurance

October 23, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos
Support for Agri-Insurance business during the COVID-19

August 19, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos
Interesting facts on agriculture and the insurance scheme of Burkina Faso

August 10, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos
Crop Insurance in France

July 23, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos
Our next stop in world Agricultural Insurance Programme is Kazakhstan

July 8, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos

Continuing our world journey, we discover the Agricultural Insurance Programme of Morocco

July 6, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos

Crop-hail insurance in Canada

June 29, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos

The structure of the BEACON Training

June 18, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos

Are you looking for transparency in Agricultural Insurance?

By beaconh2020 in hub_videos

How about jumping today over the Atlantic to the southern hemisphere, to learn a few facts regarding the Agricultural Insurance market of Argentina?

June 3, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos

Summary of the Agricultural Insurance Programme in Brazil

May 20, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos

Summary of the Agricultural Insurance Programme in Georgia

May 8, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos

BEACON Pitch presentation as a part of BEACON Training

March 30, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos

BEACON Lighthouse Customers Group (first part)

March 17, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos

How about learning a few more facts about BEACON...

November 22, 2019 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos

B2B Meetings with Lighthouse Customers and Agri-insurance professionals

October 29, 2019 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos

BEACON Targeting – Persona

July 5, 2019 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos

BEACON Lighthouse Customer Triglav Osiguranje from Serbia

June 18, 2019 By beaconh2020 in hub_videos

BEACON is a blockchain-fueled toolbox

Info Cards Section

36 BEACON info cards have been published throughout the project.

Figure 25. Content Hub Info Cards

BEACON Services can assist in agri-insurance business during the critical situations, such as the pandemic COVID-19, in:

- Provision of fast and reliable information related to risk
- Acceleration of the entire claim reporting process
- The possibility for the remote damage assessment

BEACON

BEACON Toolbox development is a co-creation process with directly involved agri-insurance players. It has a twofold role, to cover the technical and business development of the toolbox, satisfying all requirements of the demanding agri-insurance industry.

DID YOU KNOW?

BEACON

Many agri-insurance companies introduced technological innovations (usage of drones, remote sensing data) to assist with main agri-insurance procedures during the pandemic COVID-19

DID YOU KNOW?

BEACON

Multi-peril Crop Insurance Products (MPCI) dominated the crop insurance industry in 2019.

BEACON Toolbox supports the adoption of MPCI products within Agri companies' business workflows.

DID YOU KNOW?

BEACON

Several novel technologies like blockchain, machine learning, satellites, IoT are transforming the global crop insurance industry.

BEACON Toolbox incorporates most of these emerging technologies into the creation of its services.

DID YOU KNOW?

BEACON

BEACON's Damage Assessment Calculator is currently covering 4 types of risk: Hail, Flood, Drought, and Wildfires.

All behind-the-scenes functionalities are based on multiple novel methodologies like NDVI and machine-learning methods to deliver the best possible damage estimates.

BEACON

BEACON addresses the Damage Assessment challenge

BEACON quantifies one of the main challenges of Claim Based Agricultural Insurance, which is crop damage assessment.

BEACON

Damage Assessment Calculator

floods extent, delineation and damage assessment

In BEACON, SAR and optical data are utilized for flood damage assessment. SAR data assist in monitoring flood extent, damage and duration and fill the gaps of optical data acquisition. Their synergistic use enables BEACON to identify the beginning, the duration and the extent of flooding with a significant accuracy.

BEACON

Damage Assessment Calculator

hail damage assessment

For an effective hail event coverage, BEACON follows an image acquisition strategy in order to ensure that the pre- and post-damage imagery are as representative as possible of the insured crop's condition. Afterwards, the Difference Percentage Index (DPI), is calculated with the VI differencing technique, by the pre- and post-hazard satellite image. Differencing is applied on a number of optical satellite data derived indices obtained before and after a damage, that are then used to feed a machine learning model for hail quantitative damage estimation.

BEACON

Damage Assessment Calculator

fire damage assessment and grading

BEACON uses a robust severity metric applicable across broad geographic regions and fire regimes for fire detection. The Relativized Burn Ratio index derived from optical satellite data is used for fire damage assessment, mapping and severity classification. This index is designed to detect change even where pre-fire vegetation cover is low.

BEACON

Damage Assessment Calculator

the human factor in Damage Assessment

The Damage Assessment Calculator of BEACON is expected to provide timely and accurate forecasts of the potential losses and indemnities, ensure the objectivity of audit results.

Damage Assessment Calculator

According to the latest findings*, agri-insurance companies are yet to offer drought insurance.

However, they are exploring the best means of introducing it, focusing mostly on the products based on satellite data.

*https://www.researchgate.net/publication/316004766/figure/fig/1/figure-fig1:2017:316004766:55411111.png

While the main products offered on the insurance market are multi-peril, named peril and then parametric index insurance, in the case of drought, the soil moisture index insurance-based product is perceived as the most promising among Agri-insurance companies.

DID YOU KNOW?

BEACON can provide international agri-insurance companies with more precise drought-related data, presenting the BEACON Toolbox as a full package of services necessary to launch and implement the drought index insurance products in their companies.

By using the BEACON Toolbox, the satellite indices such as NDVI, Leaf Area, Chlorophyll and Yield Estimation are monitored together with the crops and parcels and further combined with the weather data in order to provide a better estimation of insured crop losses.

BEACON Yield Estimation will improve accuracy significantly beyond current alternatives by utilizing seasonal climate forecasts, predicting the trend in the next 6 months, and feeding the crop models to predict crop yield at the end of the cultivation season.

DID YOU KNOW?

BEACON Blockchain Component could process more than 10.000 policies per day, providing the automatic payouts based on previously defined thresholds – the damage percentage of affected crops.

BEACON Yield Estimation

Currently, the process of collecting yield data for agri-insurance companies, depends on taking samples of crops in defined areas, which consumes a great deal of time, resources and money.

BEACON ToolBox provides support in a yields estimation:

- Estimating more accurate crop yield risk in insured parcels
- Making insurance process more efficient
- Estimating pricing of crop yield risk more accurate
- Making more reliable sampling data combination
- Yield reduction forecasting, identifying fluctuations.

In cooperation with agri-insurance companies, BEACON offers a cutting-edge solutions to cover farmers risk exposures.

Additionally, it provides innovative protection against hail, flood, frost, draught and other calamities.

Redefining Agricultural Insurance Tools

Through the usage of BEACON Toolbox, agri insurance companies will effectively redesign their digital capabilities.

The goal is to meet the needs of their customers, at the same time creating modern and sustainable business.

Redefining Agricultural Insurance Tools

BEACON
Redefining Agricultural Insurance Tools

BEACON's Digital approach to crop insurance will mitigate the impact of weather uncertainty.

Also, it will facilitate comprehensive risk management, converting data into valuable insights.

CROP INSURANCE

Agri-insurance players can use BEACON Toolbox to integrate climate change risks into their risk management programs. BEACON Toolbox will make agri-businesses more sustainable.

BEACON
Redefining Agricultural Insurance Tools

BEACON

For agri-insurance companies, the main BEACON strengths are:

- **Advanced Weather Intelligence Service** will increase the underwriting by adjusting premiums in order to better prepare for future weather events.
- **EO services**, which provide prioritization of damages, false claim detection.
- **Smart Contract service** that increases the customer satisfaction and responsiveness to customers in general, through automation of payouts following.

When combined, they will enable **remote parcel monitoring**, especially important in times of crisis like the **COVID-19** pandemic.

BEACON

BEACON Toolbox is tested and validated within three agri-insurance companies from three different countries - **Serbia, Greece and Spain**, and one insurance broker company from Serbia.

The main results from **Serbian BEACON Pilot**:

Easy integration with the current IT systems and other supportive platforms that are already used by agri-insurance companies (e.g. GeoSrbija - Serbian national geospatial data platform).

BEACON

BEACON Toolbox is tested and validated within three agri-insurance companies from three different countries - **Serbia, Greece and Spain**, and one insurance broker company from Serbia.

The main results from **Greek BEACON Pilot**:

Early prediction of flood events and better preparation of resources of the companies.

BEACON

BEACON Toolbox is tested and validated within three agri-insurance companies from three different countries - **Serbia, Greece and Spain**, and one insurance broker company from Serbia.

The main results from **Spanish BEACON Pilot**:

Relationship of Crop soil precipitation patterns and deeper insights of climate and NDVI series.

Relevant Updates Section

54 relevant updates related to the project interest areas have been published throughout the project. See below a sample of them.

Figure 26. Content Hub Relevant Updates sample

January 17, 2022 By beaconh2020 in [hub_relevant_updates](#)
Agricultural insurance in Chile

October 27, 2021 By beaconh2020 in [hub_relevant_updates](#)
Beyond the state-of-the-art #4

December 21, 2020 By beaconh2020 in [BEACON-advantages](#), [hub_relevant_updates](#)
The BEACON toolbox is featuring @Cordis

Read more +

September 8, 2021 By beaconh2020 in hub_relevant_updates
InoSens team visit in Triglav facilities in Novi Sad, Serbia

Read more +

August 13, 2021 By beaconh2020 in hub_relevant_updates
Agricultural insurance initiatives in Southeast Asian Nations

Read more +

February 12, 2021 By beaconh2020 in hub_relevant_updates
The Armenian government expands agricultural insurance program covering 11 types of crops

Read more +

August 10, 2021 By beaconh2020 in hub_relevant_updates
Global warming increased U.S. crop insurance losses by \$27 billion in 27 years

Read more +

June 24, 2021 By beaconh2020 in hub_relevant_updates
Design Principles for Agricultural Risk Management Policies

Read more +

May 26, 2021 By beaconh2020 in hub_relevant_updates
3rd BEACON Business Case - KARAVIAS Underwriting Agency, Greece

Read more +

November 16, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_relevant_updates
Global need for advanced Early Warning Systems (EWS)

Read more +

October 7, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_relevant_updates
BEACON Toolbox as a support for agri-insurance during challenging times

Read more +

By beaconh2020 in hub_relevant_updates
BEACON's Business Shots #2

Read more +

June 16, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_relevant_updates
BEACON poll #3

Read more +

By beaconh2020 in hub_relevant_updates
BEACON Index Insurance - vol.3

Read more +

May 4, 2020 By beaconh2020 in hub_relevant_updates
BEACON newsletter #3

Read more +

December 23, 2019 By beaconh2020 in hub_relevant_updates
BEACON leaflet...

Read more +

December 9, 2019 By beaconh2020 in hub_relevant_updates
BEACON poll #1 results...

Read more +

December 4, 2019 By beaconh2020 in hub_relevant_updates
Wide range of BEACON Lighthouse Customers

3.4 Agricultural Insurance Enablers

The Agricultural Insurance (AgI) Enablers BEACON Advisory Board (AB), has been established and it operated as a counselling body consisting of external experts, aiming to provide advice and guidance for the development of the project and ensure high quality and excellence in achieving the project results. It consisted of 6 members, Dr. ATHANASIADIS Ioannis, Mrs. VAKAKI Eleni, Mr. GENILLARD Christopher, Mr. MEEUSEN Paul, Dr. ATZBERGER Clement and Ms. PANKAJ Shilpa. The members were selected on the basis of their expertise and experience in relevant to the BEACON aspects and potential contributions to the realization of current project activities.

The AgI Enablers have actively been engaged in the project, by providing written feedback and by taking part in meetings (group and person to person) and advice to BEACON partners on the quality of results throughout the implementation of the BEACON project. Overall, seven meetings have been organized as in the following:

📍 In person meetings with:

- Mrs. Eleni Vakaki on the 23rd of May 2019
- Mr. Christopher Genillard on the 23rd of May 2019
- Mr. Paul Meeusen was held on the 27th of May 2019.
- Dr. Clement Atzberger took place on the 28th of May 2019.
- Ms. Shilpa Pankaj took place on the 9th of September 2019
- Dr. Ioannis Athanasiadis took place on the 3rd of October 2019

📍 AgI Group Meeting: The BEACON AgI Enablers meeting on the 28th of June 2022

Two interviews with the AgI Enablers group using structured Questionnaires were also carried out over December 2020 and December 2021.

3.5 Lighthouse Customers

The BEACON Lighthouse Customers was a group of well-established Agricultural Insurance providers that were involved in the co-development and co-validation process of the BEACON toolbox, ensuring that the resulting tool matched the Agricultural Insurance sector workflow as well as current and future needs.

Following a series of conducted face-to-face and Skype meetings with Agricultural Insurance providers the list of BEACON Lighthouse Customers that was established, is provided below.

Table 2. Lighthouse Customers

#	Organisation	Country
1	Agrisk - crop insurance broker	HUNGARY
2	Agrupación Española de Entidades Aseguradoras de los Seguros Agrarios Combinados S.A.	SPAIN
3	AON	UK
4	ASUA	UK
5	Az Sigorta	AZERBAIJAN

#	Organisation	Country
6	B3i	SWITZERLAND
7	DDOR NOVI SAD Osiguranje	SERBIA
8	Financial and Insurance Services – Socodevi	CANADA
9	Generali Osiguranje	SERBIA
10	Genillard & Co	GERMANY
11	Halk Osiguruvanje A.D.	SKOPJE, NORTH MACEDONIA
12	HDFC ERGO General Insurance Company	INDIA
13	Hellenic Agricultural Insurance Organisation – ELGA	GREECE
14	Interamerican	GREECE
15	Microinsurance Catastrophe Risk Organisation - MiCRO	BARBADOS
16	Triglav Osiguranje	SERBIA
17	WIENER Osiguranje VIG	BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

Figure 27. Lighthouse Customers' diaspora in world map

Additionally, several big, international AgI companies were contacted, such are: Axxa, Aviva, Allianz, Agrár Biztosító, Association of Serbian Insurers, Dunav Osiguranje, Euroherc Agram Insurance, Euroherc Agram Insurance, Grawe, Groupama, as well as their branches across different countries.

As a result, the Market Outreach was expanded to the following EU countries: Germany, France, Lithuania, Italy, Liechtenstein etc. Moreover, 2 countries outside EU were contacted as well - Colombia and Brazil. Several direct AgI professionals involved into AgI business were also informed about BEACON through BEACON Market Outreach activities.

More than 50 AgI companies are informed (in total)	Approximately 150 informed AgI professionals	12 EU/outside Europe countries added
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3.6 Publications

The following 8 scientific publications have been released in peer-reviewed journals and conferences by Consortium members, achieving a 160% the relevant KPI.

Table 3. Project publications

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rivas-Tabares, D. and Tarquis Alfonso, A. M.: Joint multifractal approach to characterize nonlinear relationships of climate and cereal growth in semiarid, EGU General Assembly 2021, online, 19–30 Apr 2021, EGU21-13498, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-13498, 2021. 2. Lekakis, E., Tarquis, A. M., Kotsopoulos, S., Mygdakos, G., Dimitrakos, A., Tsioutsia, I. M., Rivas-Tabares, D., and Simeonidou, P.: Evaluation of Earth Observation Products and Their Potential for Crop Damage and Crop Loss Assessment. The Case of Beacon Project., EGU General Assembly 2021, online, 19–30 Apr 2021, EGU21-10829, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-10829, 2021. 3. Sanz Sancho, E., Saa-Requejo, A., Diaz-Ambrona, C. G., Ruiz-Ramos, M., and Tarquis, A. M.: Multifractal analysis of spatial heterogeneity in Spanish arid rangelands, EGU General Assembly 2021, online, 19–30 Apr 2021, EGU21-2698, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-2698, 2021. 4. Almeida Nauñay, A. F., Benito Zafrilla, R. M., Quemada Sáenz-Badillos, M., Losada, J. C., and Tarquis Alfonso, A. M.: Revealing climate and vegetation indices interactions through Cross Recurrence Techniques, EGU General Assembly 2021, online, 19–30 Apr 2021, EGU21-12723, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-12723, 2021. 5. Lekakis, E., Kotsopoulos, S., Mygdakos, G., Dimitrakos, A., Tsioutsia, I.M., and Simeonidou, P., 2020. Evaluation of a Satellite Drought Indicator Approach and its Potential for Agricultural Drought Prediction and Crop Loss Assessment. The Case of BEACON Project. Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies in Agriculture, Food and Environment (HAICTA 2020). Thessaloniki, Greece, September 24-27. URN: urn:nbn:de:0074-2761-0. 6. Lekakis, E., Kotsopoulos, S., Mygdakos, G., Dimitrakos, A., Tsioutsia, I.M. and Simeonidou, P., 2020. Redefining Agricultural Insurance Services Using Earth Observation Data. The Case of Beacon Project. In: Athanasiadis, I.N., Frysinger, S.P., Schimak, G. Jan Knibbe, W. (eds)
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3.8 Events' participation

BEACON was widely presented in numerous events, conferences and meetings, an indicative sample of which is listed in the following tables.

Table 4. Events' organisation and participation

Partner	Date & Place	Description	Type	Target audience	Estimated Reach (persons)	Promotional material used
ETHERISC	10-12/4/2019 Mexico City, Mexico	Virtual presentation at the "Agro Future Lab", a client event of Munich Re for most of the leading ag insurers in Latin America.	Pitch event	C-Level insurers	75	BEACON one pager

Partner	Date & Place	Description	Type	Target audience	Estimated Reach (persons)	Promotional material used
INOSENS	13-14/5/2019 Novi Sad, Serbia	Informal presentation of BEACON during the 86th international Agricultural Fair within the expert meeting on Agri-insurance and through b2b meetings with variety of AgI players [link] [link]	Stakeholder meeting	AgI players and Agri Business sector	50-70	BEACON ppt
INOSENS	14/5/2019 Novi Sad, Serbia	Ag. Fair Novi Sad, B2B meetings report, media coverage [link]	Trade fair		1,000	BEACON brochure
FCE	24/6/2019, Belgrade, Serbia	Participating in the SCERIN-7 Capacity Building Workshop on Earth System Observations: Land Cover Dynamics in the Agricultural and Protected Natural Areas in the SCERIN Domain [link]	Workshop	Scientists and other professionals based in the region or with scientific interests in the SCERIN area	100	BEACON presentation
AGROAPPS	12-13/9/2019 New Delhi, India	BEACON was presented in the 6th Asia Agriculture Insurance Conference [link]	Conference	insurers, reinsurers, service providers, brokers, regulators	110	BEACON one pager
ETHERISC	4/11/2019 Seoul, Korea	BEACON presentation at the Enterprise Ethereum and Revolution in Banking Summit 2019 [link]	Conference	Banks, insurers, blockchain startups	400	BEACON presentation
INOSENS	5/11/2019 Tomba, Hungary	Face-to-face meeting with Hungarian AgI broker - Agrisk company	Stakeholder meeting	AgI target industry players	2	BEACON presentation
FCE	22/10/2019 Zagreb, Croatia	EO data and cartography - potential for innovation - lecture and presentation at the Faculty of geodesy, University of Zagreb [link]	Expert talk	Croatian academic sector, government stakeholders in agriculture, environment & geodesy	70	
FCE	23-24/10/2019	Copernicus Hackathon Zagreb [link]	Person-to-person communication	Students, professionals, government representatives, media	100	
AGROAPPS & ETHERISC	6/11/2019 Malta	Presentation of the BEACON solution at the Decentralised Insurance Conference [link]	Conference	insurance companies, blockchain companies, ICT	200	
INOSENS	6/11/2019 Novi Sad, Serbia	"Quality of Life" [link]	Infoday	Farmers, Agri-business sector	50	BEACON presentation

Partner	Date & Place	Description	Type	Target audience	Estimated Reach (persons)	Promotional material used
UPM	28/4/2021 Hybrid	Oral presentation in EGU 2021 Conference [link]	Conference	Researchers & Academy		BEACON presentation
UPM & AGROAPPS	28/4/2021 Hybrid	Evaluation of Earth Observation Products and Their Potential for Crop Damage and Crop Loss Assessment. The Case of BEACON Project [link]	Conference	Researchers & Academy		BEACON video & abstract
UPM	28/4/2021 Hybrid	Revealing climate and vegetation indices interactions through Cross Recurrence Techniques [link]	Conference	Researchers & Academy		BEACON poster

On the 9th of February 2022, BEACON will co-organise with ENVISION, Niva4cap, e-shape, EO-WIDGET, and DIONE sister projects, an event entitled “Earth Observation services in support of agriculture and Common Agricultural Policy”. This clustering event aims to connect and explore future collaboration possibilities of European projects dealing with Earth Observation technologies for monitoring of farm management activities with regards to sustainability, in compliance with the CAP’s agri-environmental objectives, while further enhancing their visibility. The event will showcase a wide range of services and best practices delivered through several European projects.

envision

NIVA

e-shape

DIONE

BEACON

EO WIDGET

Earth Observation services in support of agriculture and Common Agricultural Policy

Wednesday,
February 9th, 2022
9:00-12:00 CET

Registration
https://us06web.zoom.us/webinar/register/WN_dNg_fPsyQXCoxDutduFQvg

- Welcome and Introduction speeches**
 - Introduction speech by the DG-AGRI representative
 - Introduction speech by the JRC representative
 - Tangible outcomes from European projects - Six European projects will present tangible outcomes related to Earth Observation monitoring: ENVISION, NIVA, e-shape, DIONE, BEACON, EO-WIDGET
- CAP monitoring - direct payments monitoring**

Earth Observation solutions for CAP monitoring, their lessons learned, expectations and future plans will be presented by Paying Agencies from Slovenia, Lithuania, Denmark, Estonia, Spain
- Earth Observation services for agriculture**

Service providers, EV ILVO, AgroApps, INRAe, NOA, Geoville Austria will present Earth Observation services for agriculture, to be used by Paying Agencies, Certification Bodies, developers, farmers and farming organisations.
- Final thoughts and future outlook**

Looking into the future of Earth Observation for CAP and agriculture, presented by European Space Agency (ESA)

Project ENVISION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869366.

Table 5. Meetings & Interviews

Partner	Date & Place/Event	Topic	Stakeholder	Comments
INOSENS	January 2019, InoSens's premises	Introduction to BEACON project and possibility to become LHC	Triglav osiguranje	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B2B meeting • Disseminated printed material
INOSENS	January 2019, InoSens's premises	Involvement into BEACON LHCs Group	Triglav osiguranje	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B2B meeting
INOSENS	February 2019, Generali Osiguranje Serbia - premises in Novi Sad	Presentation of BEACON project and BEACON pilot	Generali Osiguranje Serbia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B2B meeting • Disseminated printed GH material
INOSENS	March 2019, InoSens's premises	Pilot Description	Generali Osiguranje	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B2B Meeting • Disseminated printed GH material
INOSENS	March 2019, InoSens's premises	Introduction to BEACON project	Milenijum Osiguranje	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B2B meeting • Disseminated printed GH material
INOSENS	March 2019, DDOR Osiguranje Novi Sad premises	Introduction to BEACON project	DDOR Osiguranje Novi Sad	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B2B meeting • Disseminated printed GH material
INOSENS	April 2019, InoSens's premises, Novi Sad	Introduction to BEACON project	Wiener BiH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skype B2B meeting • BEACON ppt
INOSENS, KARAVIAS, AGROAPPS	April 2019, InoSens's premises, Novi Sad	Pilot description	Wiener BiH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skype meeting
INOSENS	May 2019, InoSens's premises	Introduction to BEACON project	Nova Osiguranje, North Macedonia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skype meeting
INOSENS	11-17 May 2019, Novi Sad, Agricultural Fair	Involvement into BEACON LHCs Group	DDOR Osiguranje Novi Sad	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B2B Meeting • Printed material
INOSENS	11-17 May 2019, Novi Sad, Agricultural Fair	BEACON - project development	Generali Osiguranje	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B2B Meeting
INOSENS	11-17 May 2019, Novi Sad, Agricultural Fair	Relationship with LHC	Triglav Osiguranje	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B2B Meeting
INOSENS	11-17 May 2019, Novi Sad, Agricultural Fair	Introduction to BEACON project	Association of Serbian Insurers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B2B Meeting • Printed material
INOSENS	11-17 May 2019, Novi Sad, Agricultural Fair	Introduction to BEACON project	COPS – Farmers cooperative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B2B Meeting • Printed material
INOSENS	11-17 May 2019, Novi Sad, Agricultural Fair	Introduction to BEACON project	Association of Serbian Insurers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B2B Meeting
INOSENS	8 October 2019, Skype Meeting	Introduction to BEACON project & LHCs group	Halk Insurance, North Macedonia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B2B meeting • Diss. GH promo digital material

3.9 Podcast

In order to enrich the audiovisual communication channels, a podcast was produced (23rd of January 2020) and communicated through the project’s website and social media.

Figure 29. Podcast channel

5. Conclusions

Although some of the targeted KPIs have not been achieved, indicators of the highest impact have been reached and surpassed. Social Media followers were higher than originally targeted, over remedying for the low success rate of the project website pageviews KPI (despite its misspecification at the proposal stage, the project pushed hard for its enhancement). Social Media are more user-friendly tool and can impact greater numbers of target groups, making the disseminated information readily available to the interested parties. Dissemination wise the successful outcome of this KPI is of great importance.

Additionally, the consortium successfully managed to reach and surpass indicators focusing on in written engagements, specific stakeholder groups like Newsletter recipients, business blog posts, videos released, forums presentations and business journals publications. A large number of meetings were carried out with AgI, EO, Farmers Organisations, and EU Institutions. Some KPIs were significantly impacted by the social distancing measures of the pandemic like distribution of printed materials and person-to-person meetings.

Overall, the promotional activities and engagement of stakeholders can be assessed as highly successful. Systematic and organized dissemination activities managed to effectively:

- ⊗ Raise awareness and openly demonstrate clear economic, social, and environmental benefits of utilizing/adopting BEACON solution within the AgI market.
- ⊗ Build a sustainable customer base for future expansion.
- ⊗ Demonstrate the significance and business opportunities deriving from utilizing EO derived data in new products and services within new sectors/markets.
- ⊗ Disseminate the respective project outcomes to the widest possible community of potential beneficiaries.

